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EFFECT OF STUDENTS' TEAM ACHIEVEMENT DIVISION (STAD) ON STUDENTS' INTEREST IN TAXATION IN UNIVERSITIES IN CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract

The need to enhance students' performance in Taxation necessitated this study to determine the effect of Students' Team Achievement Division (STAD) on the interest of students in Taxation in universities in Cross River State of Nigeria. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a pre-test, post-test, control group, quasi-experimental research design. The population used for the study consisted of 93 final year business education students in the study area. The population was used as the sample for the study based on its manageable size. The instrument for data collection was a 22-item Taxation Interest Inventory (TII). Two Business Educators and one Measurement and Evaluation expert, all from Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki validated the instrument, and the reliability was carried out using Cronbach Alpha Statistic which yielded a coefficient of 0.87. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and determine the spread of the data collected while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was employed to test the null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed that students taught with STAD had a higher interest in Taxation than those taught with the conventional method and students that were taught with STAD did not show any pronounced differential effect based on gender. Also, there was no interaction effect of treatment and gender on the students' and interest in Taxation. It was concluded that STAD is a suitable method for improving students' interest in Taxation, and should be used in teaching Taxation. Based on the findings, it was recommended that students should take advantage of STAD in order to boost their interest in taxation.

Keywords: *Students' team achievement division (STAD), Interest, Taxation, Conventional teaching method, Learners.*

Introduction

Countries of the world that have made great advancement in their socio-political and economic

landscape are those that have laid much credence to the educational sector as it is widely known that no nation can rise above the quality of its teachers and

the entire educational system. Education is a means of socializing people in a community of global knowledge and skills for sustainable economic growth as well as for the modification and changes of the same in conformity with the already laid down ideologies (Danjuma, 2013). The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FGN, 2014) averred that education is the most crucial tool for bringing about change and also a masterful tool for advancing national development. It is practically impossible to talk about education of individuals without talking about the concept of teaching and learning. The process of teaching is active and constructive, and the teacher plays the part of a strategic planner, selecting the subject matter and the most effective teaching methods (Oyetunde, 2014). Gidado, Abdullahi and Adamu (2016) explained that the productivity of teachers, which has to do with teaching and the knowledge and skills acquired by the learners, determine the quality of a nation's educational system. Gidado, et al asserted that teaching has to do with the exchange of ideas between teachers and learners. The purpose of this interaction is to bring about desirable changes in the students' behaviour using various instructional strategies and manipulative resources in ways to maximize students' learning (Das, 2013). This means that, for learning to take place after rigorous teaching, the methods, techniques and instructional strategies adopted in the teaching-learning process must be appropriate and suitable.

The study of the course Taxation may be described as complex when compared to the study of other accounting courses in Business Education. This complexity in the teaching and learning of taxation may be as a result of too many figures (numeric data) that need calculation and computation. Taxation is a practical accounting course that requires both teacher and learner to have sound knowledge of principles and procedures that guide the calculation, preparation and computation of tax related statements. This implies that, before any

figure is calculated and a tax statement computed, several principles and procedures must be followed. This makes the teaching and learning of a daunting task.

Tax, taxation and tax administration are paramount features in a nation's economic success. There is hardly any economy in the world today that completely absolves its citizens from the payment of tax, the least they could do is to give tax haven to a particular group of people or manufacturers for a period of time. This shows how important taxation is to governments of different countries of the world. Institute of Chartered Accountants Nigeria (ICAN, 2016) outlined the importance and rationale for Taxation as follows:

- ✓ Redistribution of income and wealth to society's members through payments and benefits.
- ✓ Promoting social and economic welfare by playing a role towards provision of ~~in~~ providing merit goods like health and education (although these merit goods can be provided privately).
- ✓ Ensuring economic stability since taxes are used to stabilize inflation and unemployment, and regulate producers and protect consumers. For example, the imposition of more taxes on tobacco producing companies in order to restrict the production and consumption of the product and the provision of public goods.

ICAN (2016) further highlighted the core objectives of Taxation to include revenue generation, redistribution of income and wealth, economic regulation to provide infrastructure and economic welfare and harmonization of taxes. Taxation provides the government with revenue needed to run the economy and, therefore, is very to the citizens. It is, therefore, pertinent that the most suitable and appropriate methods should be adopted when teaching or learning Taxation in the universities considering its crucial role in the economy of the country. The right application of methods and techniques in teaching taxation will enable the

learners to gain the required knowledge, skills, and competencies to achieve the goals and objectives of the course.

In recent times, there appears to be a high demand for vocational skills rather than non-vocational skills. This could be occasioned by the drive for entrepreneurship in the world economy. The study of taxation under financial accounting is one of the subjects that could provide such vocational skills that are presently sought after. However, it has been observed that interest of students in the study of taxation has continued to dwindle over time due to its complex nature. Simeon (2019) revealed that, undergraduate students of accounting regard the study of Taxation boring, unexciting and more difficult than other accounting courses like Financial Accounting, Management Accounting and Auditing. This lack of interest in vocational subject like taxation that is much sought after may not be the fears of the researcher alone as Anyim (2012) noted that there is a growing frustration in Nigeria as a society about the non-performance of the hopes and aspirations of the citizens (the learners). Anyim maintained that the fallen standard of education has been a household issue and the media is not left out in rolling out these unpleasant beats.

Apart from the nature of Taxation, a number of other factors may be contributing in the persistent waning of students' interest in the study of the course. According to Agube (2019) posited that factors like use of –inappropriate teaching methods, lack of teaching skills, inadequate instructional facilities, poor learning environment and students' attitude towards learning are some of causative factors to dwindling lack of students' interest in the study of Taxation. Among these factors, using inappropriate teaching methods and techniques seems to be the most pronounced factor. Aladejena (2018) observed university lecturers still retain the old conservative approach of teaching, with them being in full control. The traditional or conventional method of

teaching focuses on the teacher as the controller of the learning environment. The teacher holds the power and responsibility, so they serve as the instructor and make decisions regarding the creation of curriculum content and the learning outcome.

The traditional teaching methods, including the lecture method, regard students as having 'knowledge hole' that needs to be filled with information, with teachers acting as repertoire of knowledge and students as dormant recipients who only listen to what is taught, copy notes, carry out class work and complete their assignments (Agbor, 2020). Okon (2017) enumerated the disadvantages of the lecture method to include: focusing on the teacher rather than the learner, allowing for no initiative on the side of pupils, stimulating just the auditory sense, limiting learning and retention, and violating the principles of learning by doing, among other things. Okon (2017) averred that the disadvantages of the lecture method outweigh the advantages. The lecture method is predominantly used in teaching Taxation in the university. This instructional method has fallen short of current realities as it does not meet international standards and global best practices. This calls for the promotion of student/learner-centered instructional strategies such as cooperative learning to meet modern realities and boost students' interest in Taxation.

Students' Team Achievement Division (STAD) is a cooperative model in which students with different levels of academic abilities are put into little groups to work and learn together in order to accomplish a task. STAD was formulated by R. E. Slavin, a lecturer at John Hopkins University (Tran, 2013). It is an instructional strategy that allows the teacher to heterogeneously assign about four or five or even more members into small groups to perform and complete certain tasks as prescribed by the teacher. Learners in these small learning groups are mixed according to ~~in~~ their level of performance and

abilities, gender, ethnicity and interest (Tiatong & Teemuangsai, 2013). In STAD, the teacher introduces a lesson after the formation of the small groups, and then creates a task or an activity based on the lesson presented in order to stimulate the spirit of team work on the task(s) for the students to work as a team and not individually. Jamaludin & Mokhtar (2018) pointed out that these tasks can progress from simpler to more complex tasks. When working on the task(s), students are required to help each other until all members of the group have mastered the task(s). Due to teams' cooperation, the students in each learning group are excited to learn and equally help each other to learn, and ultimately realize the goals and objectives of the lesson, thereby becoming successful (Khan & Inamullah, 2011). Karacop (2016) concluded that, in Students' Team Achievement Division, cooperative contribution to the success of the team is profound and in the foreground.

According to Hartati (2017), one of the gains of employing STAD is that, it boosts students' self-confidence as students begin to feel that they are more in control of their academic success. In the teaching or learning of taxation and indeed any other field of study, the interest of the students is paramount. Taxation, like mathematics, scares students a lot because of the computation of so many figures. The nature of the subject makes students to lose interest in studying the course. The teaching methods employed by the teacher in the presentation of taxation materials to be learnt may determine the level of interest that the learners will put into studying the course. Where suitable instructional methods or techniques are employed in the teaching and learning process, interest of students may increase but where the unsuitable methods are employed, students' interest in the course may depreciate. Achor and Orji (2019) revealed that interest is a motivational construct. This means that interest can be stirred up as a result of efforts to

satisfy a felt need. Adejon and Idachaba (2010) affirmed that for students to acquire relevant knowledge and skills in Taxation, teachers need to replace conventional teaching methods with modern methods that stimulate and sustain students' interest to enhance their academic achievement and equip them for success in employment on graduation. This is because the absence of interest and motivation is obvious in the rate at which students neglect their studies or treat academic work with obvious levity (Otoo, Iddrisu, Kessie and Larbi, 2018). It is with this backdrop that this study on the effect of STAD as a cooperative learning instructional strategy on the academic interest of students in taxation in Universities in Cross River State was conceived.

Statement of the Problem

It has been observed that students' interest in the study of Taxation in universities in Cross River State is dwindling over the years. This could be the core reason for their declining academic achievement in the course which is creating a mismatch between the demand of the market and the supply of skillful accountants who will act in the capacity of tax administrators in the industry. The study of Taxation may be described as complex when compared to the study of other accounting courses in university Business Education programme. This complexity in the teaching and learning of taxation is viewed to be because it involves too many figures (numeric data) that need calculation and computation. The nature of the course coupled with the teacher-centered methods (lecture method) predominantly used by lecturers could be responsible for the dwindling interest of students in it over the years. Students' interest is a motivational factor which drives them to learn and learning rarely occurs without motivation. The lecture teaching method has been found to be unsuitable for teaching and learning of Taxation. In this regard, researchers have called for adoption of student-centered teaching methods such as Students' Team Achievement Division (STAD). STAD is a

type of the cooperative teaching methods in which students are arranged to learn together as a team in small groups to assist each other. The problem of this study, however, is that the extent STAD will stimulate and sustain students' interest in the study of Taxation is not clearly known. This requires an empirical study such as this study on the effect of STAD on students' interest in taxation in universities in Cross River State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the effect of Students' Team Achievement Division on students' interest in taxation in Universities in Cross River State. Specifically, the study sought to investigate the;

1. Effect of Students' Team Achievement Division on the mean interest scores of students in Taxation.
2. Effects of Students' Team Achievement Division on the mean interest scores of male and female students in Taxation.
3. Interaction effect of treatment and gender on the students' mean interest in Taxation.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the effect of Students' Team Achievement Division on the mean interest scores of students in Taxation?
2. What is the mean interest score of male and female students taught Taxation using Students' Team Achievement Division?
3. What is the interaction effect of treatment and gender on the students' mean interest scores in Taxation?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of students taught Taxation using Students' Team Achievement Division and those taught using conventional teaching method.

2. There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of male and female students taught Taxation using students' team achievement division and those taught using conventional teaching method.

3. The interaction effect of treatment and gender on students' mean interest scores in Taxation will not be significant.

Methods

The study adopted a pre-test, post-test, control group, quasi-experimental research design. The population used for the study consisted of 93 final year business education students in the study area. The population was used as the sample for the study based on its manageable size. The instrument for data collection was a 22-item Taxation Interest Inventory (TII). Two Business Educators and one Measurement and Evaluation expert, all from Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki validated the instrument, and the reliability was carried out using Cronbach Alpha Statistic which yielded a coefficient of 0.87. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and determine the spread of the data collected while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was employed to test the null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance.

Experimental Procedure

Before the treatment, the interest inventory was administered to the treatment group as well as the control group. This helped the researcher to determine the level of students' interest in taxation and to also ascertain the homogeneity of the experimental group. Cross River University of Technology was used as the treatment group while the control group was the University of Calabar based on balloting.

Two instructional approaches were employed during the experiment: The conventional instructional strategy and Students' Team Achievement Division (STAD). The control group was taught taxation with the conventional lecture method while the treatment

group was taught taxation using Students' Team Achievement Division. The control group was taught by their regular taxation lecturer while the treatment group was also taught by their regular lecturer but also supervised by the researcher himself. The same scheme of work was utilized in both groups (contents and study materials were the same)

The treatment group was presented with the lessons during the first session. The first session was at the beginning of each topic per week, then, the class was thereafter assigned into groups of five to form a team. In this session, students engaged in presentations of contents in order to understand the materials given to them. They discussed the lessons and materials given to them by the researcher. Members of each group with better understanding helped other team members catch up with lessons

and materials. They worked with members of their team until all team members have mastered the lessons and materials to a certain level. In the process of working as a team, learners helped each other by using multiple learning resources like mobile apps for learning, browsing the internet, utilizing textbooks and other learning resources that they found comfortable for them in order to enhance their group discussion and develop creativity.

This procedure continued for a duration of six (6) weeks after which the taxation interest inventory was re-administered to both control and treatment groups. The scores gotten from the responses to the Interest Inventory from the control and treatment group provided data for answering the research questions as well as testing the research hypotheses.

Results

Table 1: Post-test Mean Interest Scores of Students in Taxation based on Teaching Methods

Methods	No.	\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X} diff
Students' Team Achievement Division	43	71.88	3.36	31.26
Conventional Teaching Method	50	40.62	3.00	

Table 1 shows that students that were taught with STAD had a mean interest score of 71.88 and a standard deviation of 3.36 while students that were taught with the conventional teaching method had a mean interest score of 40.62 and a standard deviation

of 3.00. This shows a mean interest score of 31.26 in favour of the treatment group which implies that STAD is a suitable method for improving students' interest in Taxation.

Table 2: Mean Interest Scores of Students based on Gender

Gender	No.	\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X} diff
Male	19	72.18	3.94	0.51
Female	24	71.67	2.88	

Table 2 shows that students that were taught with STAD did not show any pronounced differential effect in their interest based on gender. The result reveals that male students had a mean interest score of 72.18 and a standard deviation of 3.94 while the

female students had a mean interest score of 71.67 and a standard deviation of 2.88. This shows a mean interest score difference of 0.51 which implies that STAD is a suitable method for improving both male and female students' interest in Taxation.

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Table 3: Mean Interest Scores of Students based on Interaction effect of Methods and Gender

Gender	Male	Female
Methods	Mean	Mean
Students' Team Achievement Division	72.16	71.67
Conventional Teaching Method	40.19	40.93

Table 3 shows that male students from the STAD group had a mean interest score of 72.16 while the female students from the same group had a mean score of 71.67. In like manner, the male students from the conventional group had a mean score of

40.19 while the female students from the same group had a mean score of 40.93. With this result, there is no interaction effect of teaching methods and gender on the mean interest scores of students in Taxation.

Table 4: ANCOVA Results on Students' Interest Based on Interaction Effect Between Treatment and Gender.

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Sqaure	F	Sig of F
Corrected Model	22621.381 ^a	4	5655.345	559.752	.000
Intercept	1689.512	1	1689.512	167.224	.000
PreInterest	15.868	1	15.868	1.571	.213
Method	22210.055	1			
Gender	.002		.002	.000	.988
Method & Gender	5.426	1	5.426	.537	.466
Error	889.092	88	10.103		
Total	305606.000	93			
Corrected Total	23510.473	92			

a. R Squared = .962 (Adjusted R Squared = .960)
 According to the findings in Table 4 above, the P-value of 0.000 for hypothesis 1 is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Since the P-value must be larger than 0.05 in order to be accepted, the null hypothesis must be rejected if it is less than that threshold of significance. With this result, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected. This suggests that the mean interest scores of students who learned about

taxes via STAD and those who learned it the traditional way differ significantly. The P-value for hypothesis 3 is 0.466 at 0.05 alpha, which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. As a result, the null hypothesis is retained because the P-value must be less than 0.05 in order for the null hypothesis to be rejected. This indicates that there is no interaction between approaches and gender in terms of how interested students are in taxation.

Table 5: ANCOVA Results on Students' Interest Based on Gender

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Sqaure	F	Sig of F
Corrected Model	11.148 ^a	2	5.574	.481	.622
Intercept	1397.319	1	1397.319	120.648	.000

PreInterest	8.589	1	8.589	.742	.394
Gender	2.485	1	2.485	.215	.646
Error	463.271	40	11.582		
Total	222667.000	43			
Corrected Total	260.605	42			

a. R Squared = .023 (Adjusted R Squared = -.025)
 According to the data in Table 5 above, the P-value of 0.646 is greater than the threshold of significance of 0.05. The null hypothesis is thus maintained because the decision rule states that accepting the null hypothesis when the P-value is larger than 0.05 level of significance. As a result, there is no discernible difference between male and female students studying taxation using STAD in terms of mean interest scores.

Discussion

Effect of Students’ Team Achievement Division on the mean interest scores of students in Taxation.

Table 1 shows that students that were taught with STAD did not show any pronounced differential effect in their interest based on gender. The result reveals that male students had a mean interest score of 72.18 and a standard deviation of 3.94 while the female students had a mean interest score of 71.67 and a standard deviation of 2.88. This shows a mean interest score difference of 0.51 which implies that STAD is a suitable method for improving both male and female students’ interest in Taxation.

Also, analysis in Table 4 rejected the null hypothesis, meaning that there is a significant difference in the mean interest score of students taught Taxation using STAD and those taught using the conventional teaching strategy. The results concur with those of Kpolovi, Joe, and Okoto's (2014) study, which found significant correlation and multiple predictions of students' academic achievement. When STAD was used as the teaching method, the predictor variables accounted for 21.60% of the variance in students' academic

achievement, and this prediction is statistically significant (p0.5) at 2 and 515 degrees of freedom (df). This demonstrates that a student's attitude toward school and enthusiasm in learning can both independently contribute significantly to the prediction of their academic success. Thus, one can conveniently say that educators should adopt STAD as a teaching strategy because it has the ability to improve students’ interest in learning and attitude towards school; thereby ultimately contributing in boosting their performance academically.

Effect of Students’ Team Achievement Division on the mean interest scores of male and Female students in Taxation.

Table 2 shows that students that were taught with STAD did not show any pronounced differential effect in their interest based on gender. The result reveals that male students had a mean interest score of 72.18 and a standard deviation of 3.94 while the female students had a mean interest score of 71.67 and a standard deviation of 2.88. This shows a mean interest score difference of 0.51 which implies that STAD is a suitable method for improving both male and female students’ interest in Taxation. This showed that STAD instructional strategy enhance the interest of both male and female students. The results of this study are consistent with Okafor's (2011) assertion that male interests have not outweighed those of their female counterparts in a field that was previously thought to be male-oriented. This may be partially responsible for the rise in the number of women working in this field. If the performance of women in the field is a motivating factor for more women to enroll in accounting, then more research may be needed in this area. There is proof that, even

at the professional body level, the enrollment and pass rates for women have been rising. One of the advantages of students' team achievement division is that it fosters unity amongst students thereby increasing their interest level irrespective of gender.

The interactive effect of teaching strategies and gender on the mean interest scores of

Students in Taxation.

The results of analysis as presented in Table 3 showed that male and female students taught Taxation using Students' Team Achievement Division showed higher interest than their counterparts taught using conventional teaching method. There is no interaction effect between strategies and gender because the effectiveness of STAD strategy remained superior across gender and groups. Additionally, Table 5's analysis supported the null hypothesis, indicating that there was no interaction between the gender of the teacher and the students' mean interest in taxation. The findings are in agreement with the findings of the study of Nurhayai and Hartono (2017) who reported that the ability and interest in mathematical concepts was better with both male and female students who used the cooperative learning model of STAD than with the male and female students who used the Realistic Mathematical Education (RME). It can be safe to say that the Cooperative learning model of STAD be considered as one of the learning models that can be applied by the teacher in taxation learning because of its effectiveness in helping students train their ability and interest in understanding taxation concepts as compared to other teaching methods.

Conclusion

Student Team Achievement Division (STAD) is one of the innovative instructional strategies that allowed the researcher to create small groups among learners in which each member of the group work together on a common task to achieve the common goal. Before and after this procedure, test were administered to the students in comparison with students taught with

the conventional method. It was discovered that students that were taught with STAD had higher mean interest score than the students that were taught with the conventional teaching method. Since the mean interest score was in favour of the treatment group, it was concluded that STAD is a suitable method for improving students' interest in Taxation, and should be used in teaching Taxation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- 1 Students should take advantage of the use of STAD in order to boost their interest level in Taxation.
- 2 In creating different groups of STAD, the Educator should endeavour to be gender sensitive. There should be a mixture of both male and female students in a particular team, which will help to increase the interest of both gender.
- 3 The school administrators should provide the enabling environment for in-service training for Taxation lecturers to equip themselves with the skills needed to increase the interest of both male students and female students with the utilization of STAD.

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